

Mutually Exclusive Probabilities, Nonlocality, Quantum Interference, Spatial Periodicity and the Removal of Time

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The classical theory of probability seems to deal with real probabilities describing mutually exclusive events (e.g. a heads up or down for a coin). Quantum mechanics deals with spatially nonlocal mutually exclusive events. Thus, an integral over space is needed to determine the mutual exclusivity. This suggests periodic functions which describe the mutually periodic (orthogonal) scenarios and so give rise to positive and negative conditional probabilities. Furthermore the idea of squaring a conditional probability arises as one conditional probability may contain another in certain situations. By squaring $W^*(x)W(x)$ and integrating, one finds if interference terms are mutually exclusive or not.

Given nonlocality, various positive and negative probabilities may locally add or subtract to give a local interference pattern. Even when squaring the conditional probabilities e.g. $W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction, a spatially periodic pattern remains. Finally, time seems to be removed from the time-independent quantum scenario so past and future events may interfere as in a time-dependent scattering scenario.

We try to investigate these linked ideas of quantum theory.

Mutual Exclusivity, Nonlocality and Periodicity

Classical probability theory deals with real probabilities which add to 1 and represent mutually exclusive events e.g. a heads up or down coin. Quantum mechanics, on the other hand, deals with nonlocality with respect to mutually exclusive situations. Thus a wavefunction:

$$W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

refers to different momentum states p , but these are not discerned locally. One must integrate over all space to find that $\exp(ip_1 x)$ and $\exp(ip_2 x)$ are mutually exclusive i.e. orthogonal. This mutual exclusivity is given by an integral over space equal to zero which suggests periodic functions to achieve this result. It is possible to have a strictly positive or negative function multiplied by a periodic function yield zero, but all functions should be on the same footing it seems. A strictly positive or negative function multiplied by another of the same type does not integrate to zero. Thus periodicity, which is a signature of quantum mechanics, seems to be closely linked to nonlocality in determining mutually exclusive scenarios. $\exp(ipx)$ is one example of a periodic function as is $\exp(-im\phi)$ and $P_l(\cos(\theta))$ from the Legendre function which appears in spherical harmonics.

It is unusual that one must examine all space points (i.e. integrate over space a product of probabilities to determine mutually exclusive events). This process, however, suggests that two probability schemes are at work. The first is the nonlocal scheme which does not use real values (as it is not classical) and does not locally discern between potentially exclusive situations. For example, $\exp(ip_1 x)$ and $\exp(ip_2 x)$ do not discern p_1 and p_2 at x . To prove the two are mutually exclusive one must multiply them together and integrate over all space. This

suggests a rule for finding probabilities related to classical probabilities for mutually exclusive scenarios. One may have $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$, but:

$$\int W^*(x)W(x) dx = 1 = \sum_p a^*(p)a(p) \quad ((2))$$

This suggests that $a^*(p)a(p)$ (guaranteed to be real and less than one) represents a classical probability i.e. $P(p)$.

It may be noted that by using nonlocal probabilities $\exp(ipx)$, one takes the opposite point of view of classical physics in which one follows a particle at each $x(t)$. In fact we argue that the nonlocal probabilities even remove time from the calculation as we try to demonstrate in the next section.

Time-Independent Scattering

Consider first the classical mechanical view of scattering from a potential. A particle at a position x_1 at t_1 moves in a straight line until it reaches the potential edge at x_2 at t_2 and then scatters. Time as well as a specific point in space i.e. the potential edge are critical in this picture. The particle has a certain probability to be scattered (either forward or backwards) and a probability to pass through.

Quantum time-independent scattering is different. It removes time completely and considers conditional probabilities for the incoming beam and the scattered particles i.e.

$$W(r) = \exp(ikxz) + f(\theta, \phi) \exp(ikr)/r \quad ((3)) \quad (\text{see (1)})$$

One may note that these conditional probabilities consist of various periodic quantities such as $\exp(ikz)$ and $\exp(ikr)$. Both terms in ((3)) exist at all points in space with the latter representing both forward and backward scattered particles. The former $\exp(ikz)$, however, represents the incoming beam which exists at all z points which is unusual. First, at $x = -\infty$ there should only be the incoming beam because no scattering has occurred, but as noted above time is completely removed from the quantum time independent scenario. Secondly, if one calculates $W^*(r)W(r)$ there exists an interference term between the incoming beam and the scattered beam i.e.

$$\exp(-ikz) f(\theta, \phi) \exp(ikr)/r + \exp(ikz) f(\theta, \phi) \exp(-ikr)/r \quad ((4))$$

For $z \rightarrow -\infty$ it is as if the future is interfering with the past, but as argued time is removed from such a picture. This means that when one integrates over space to find information about classical type probabilities, $\exp(ikz)$ (a conditional probability) may contain the scattered probability within it so that the interference integral is nonzero. (This assumes that various scattering results are orthogonal functions).

$$\text{One may note that (1): } \exp(ikz) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (2l+1) j_l(kr) P_l(\cos(\theta)) \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{and (1) } f(\theta) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (2l+1) a_l(k) P_l(\cos(\theta)) \quad ((6))$$

It is noted in (1) that: $l_{max} \approx k r_0$ where r_0 is the range of the potential.

As an example, consider $l_{max}=1$ and nonspherical scattering i.e. no $l=0$ piece. Then $f(\theta)$ is proportional to $f_1(\cos(\theta))$ and this term is also contained in $\exp(ikz)$. Thus:

$$[\exp(ikz) + f(\theta)\exp(ikr)/r]^* [\exp(ikz) + f(\theta)\exp(ikr)/r]$$

$$= \int_{\text{space}} 1 + \int_{\text{space}} \frac{1}{r^2} f(\theta)f(\theta) + \int_{\text{space}} \text{Interference term}$$

from ((4)) ((7))

1 is the incoming flux, the second term is the amount of scattered particles (both forward and backward) and the interference term is nonzero because $P_1(\cos(\theta))$ from $f(\theta)$ integrates with $P_1(\cos(\theta))$ from the expansion of $\exp(ikx)$. All other terms yield zero because $P_1(\cos(\theta))$ is orthogonal to all other $P_l(\cos(\theta))$ terms. This is again an example to nonlocality and mutual exclusivity reached by integrating over all space. $j_l(kr)$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$ and $\exp(ikr)$ terms become related i.e. from (1) $j_l(kr) \rightarrow [r=\infty] \sin(kr - l\pi/2)/kr$.

Physically one expects ((7)) to yield:

$$\text{The amount of scattered particles} + [1(\text{incoming beam}) - \text{amount of scattered particles}] \quad ((8))$$

This way the number of particles before equals the number after. This result is obtained through the unusual nonlocal scheme of time-independent quantum mechanics where $\exp(ikz)$ contains the scattered probability plus other terms. Interference then yields the minus of the scattered term so one has:

$$1 - \text{scattered particles} + \text{scattered particles} = 1 \text{ the initial number of particles}$$

This result is already well-known in the literature i.e. that interference of the scattering term with the incoming beam yields minus the scattered particles so the number of particles is conserved. This result is obvious in classical physics, but classical physics contains no probabilities that add or any interference or nonlocal exclusivity which appears through integration over space. In quantum mechanics, the result follows immediately if one assumes that the incoming beam conditional probability contains the conditional probability of the scattering result plus orthogonal terms. One is then forced to square the conditional probability so there can be product terms (including the interference) which when integrated yields the negative of the scattered term.

Thus the entire picture seems to be one of orthogonal (periodic) functions used to create conditional probabilities such that the "past" function e.g. $\exp(ikz)$ already contains the future conditional probability ($P_1(\cos(\theta))$) and other orthogonal terms. No time appears in this calculation, only various physical type conditional probabilities.

Bound Particles

The above scenario is interesting in that it may suggest a way to look at a particle in an infinite potential well. Classically, a particle would start from one end, move to the other and elastically rebound. Thus, k and $-k$ would exist at mutually exclusive times. Time-independent quantum mechanics removes time from the picture so $\exp(ikx)$ and $\exp(-ikx)$, conditional probabilities, may interfere with each other at each point even though they are mutually exclusive. (This occurs for all $\exp(ikx)$ used to create the solution: $[\exp(ikx) + \exp(-ikx)]/2$.) Thus one may not think classically and ask how a positive k may interfere with a $-k$ when they exist at different times. The two are periodic to ensure mutual exclusivity when integrated over x , but they add and subtract at different places to form $2 \cos(kx)$ which has humps and troughs. In other words the periodicity from the nonlocal conditional probabilities (which ensures mutual exclusivity i.e. spatial integrals of 0) also creates hump-like patterns within space. Thus $W^*(x)W(x)$ often displays these humps as in bound state solutions and the two slit interference experimental results.

Physically Why Should there be Nonlocality and Periodicity?

We try to argue that quantum mechanical humps and troughs occur when there is a reaction (either with $V(x)$ or with the two slit walls which are a kind of $V(x)$ etc). Usually $V(x)$ describes local changes in a particle i.e. $F = -dV/dx$ according to classical mechanics. If one wishes to have an impulse picture which on average yields $V(x)$, a smooth function, one may employ $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ and a similar result for the particle $\exp(ipx)$ which creates $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ which is used to create the smooth function $KE(x)$ (kinetic energy). Thus physically the periodicity in $\exp(ipx)$ (which leads to orthogonal functions) seems to be linked to $\exp(ipx)$ acting as a kind of potential probability just as $\exp(ikx)$ in $V(x)$ because both $\exp(ikx)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ of a quantum particle may deliver potential hits. Given that quantum mechanics is a probabilistic nonlocal theory, one does not worry about following a particle from one point to another, but the periodic pattern which appears in $W^*(x)W(x)$ is certainly unusual as indicates that there is little probability to find the particle at trough regions even though the average kinetic energy in such regions $-1/2m [d/dx dW/dx]W$ is the same classical result as at the high probability peaks. The humps are physically indicative of a nonlocal probability system which uses periodicity to create mutual exclusiveness over all space, but not at local points. Physically one may think of the quantum particle probability $\exp(ipx)$ as that of a potential which delivers p momentum impulses rather than as a particle moving from x_1, t_1 to x_2, t_2 .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that classical probabilities are real because they represent mutually exclusive scenarios. Quantum mechanics on the other hand is nonlocal; one has to integrate over space products of conditional probabilities to show they are mutually exclusive i.e. the integral is zero. This suggests conditional probabilities are periodic to achieve this "orthogonality" or mutual exclusiveness. Time is also completely removed from the picture, so conditional probabilities of events which should classically happen at different times may be

added together. Once various conditional probabilities have been added, the modulus squared of the result may be taken to find a function which may be integrated over space to yield mutually exclusive results. The reason the modulus squared $W^*(x)W(x)$ is used is to allow for interference terms, which are products of different conditional probabilities, to be evaluated. It is possible that one conditional probability may contain the other plus extra orthogonal terms and thus yield a nonvanishing interference term when integrated over space. The periodicity of conditional probabilities seems to physically arise because quantum particles may be seen as delivering impulse hits (i.e. act like a impulse hits within a smooth potential $V(x)$) and yet must create a smooth $KE(x)$ (kinetic energy) in the same manner that $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k \text{ } V_k \exp(ikx)$ where $V_k \exp(ikx)$ delivers an impulse hit of k .

References

1. Shankar, R. Principles of Quantum Mechanics (Plenum, 1988)